

The suppressive powers of the anionic surfactants are in the following order :

Manoxol-OT > Tergitol-7 > Sodium lauryl sulphate > Manoxol-IB and Methyl red > XL-anionic > Dodecyl benzene sulphonate.

The suppressive powers of 2-ethoxy ethanol and ethyl dagol, are least among the non-ionic surfactants used. This is due to their low molecular weights. The efficacies of these neutral surfactants are in the following order :

Triton X-100 > Decon-90 > Amido black > Ethyldiagol > 2-ethoxyethanol.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Sulphadimethoxin Salicylaldehyde through its Copper Chelate

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SULPHONAMIDES are drugs of established therapeutic value. Butler and Ingle¹ have condensed sulphonamides with salicylaldehyde and have isolated various sulphonamide Salicylaldehydes. Tsukamoto and Yuhi^{2,3} have condensed sulphadiazine, Sulphamerazine and Sulphamethazine with 5 Bromo salicylaldehyde and 3, 5 dibromo salicylaldehyde. He also studied antibacterial activity of these bromo salicylaldehydes and found them to be active against mycobacterium tuberculosis. The complexes of Sulphadiazines salicylaldehydes have been studied with copper, nickel and cobalt by Jain and Chaturvedi⁴⁻⁶ and found 2 : 1 complexation.

Cupric ions react with SUDMSA forming a green coloured complex soluble in 50% ethanol. Based on this colour reaction a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for SUDMSA by which SUDMSA can be determined upto 50 μ g.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade. Sulphadimethoxin salicylaldehyde (SUDMSA) was prepared as described earlier⁷.

Absorbance measurements were made on a Beckmann model DV spectrophotometer and pH of the solution were checked using a pH meter (Beckmann model H-2). The pH of the solutions were adjusted by using different buffer solutions.

To prepare $1 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution, 41.4 mg. of SUDMSA was dissolved in 1 lit. of ethanol. The stock solution of copper was prepared using Analar grade copper acetate.

Results and Discussion

Sulphadimethoxin salicylaldehyde is light yellow in colour. The absorption spectra of SUDMSA shows three absorption bands at 222 nm, 241 nm and 278 nm. The complex is deep green in colour with an absorption maximum at 380 nm. at pH 6.5 which remains unaltered irrespective of the molar ratio of the components of the solution. This indicates the presence of only one complex in the solution under the conditions of study. The absorption by Copper acetate at λ_{max} of the complex is very low. The absorbance vs. pH plot shows that the absorption of the complex remains constant between pH 6-8. Thus a pH around 6.5 was kept for spectrophotometric study. The mole ratio plot shows that half moles of copper are sufficient for full colour development thus indicating that the metal and ligand are present in 1 : 2 ratio in the complex.

The system adheres to Beer's law.

Procedure : Take a suitable aliquot of SUDMSA solution in a 10 ml. volumetric flask, add sufficient excess of copper solution, 2 ml. Buffer solution followed by alcohol and water, so that final solution contains 50% (V/V) alcohol ; measure the absorbance at nm.

In this way it was possible to determine SUDMSA upto 50 μ g. quantities.

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